

Complexes of Zinc(II) and Cadmium(II) with 2-Pyridine Ethanol

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A number of complexes of the type ML_2X_n (where $x = Cl^-, Br^-, I^-, NO_2^-, SCN^-$ and OAC^-) of zinc and cadmium with 2-pyridine ethanol were prepared. Attempts have been made to characterise these compounds and their molecular compositions and possible structures determined on the basis of analytical data, conductance and i.r. spectra.

PYRIDINE and some of its derivatives have been used in the estimation of various metals through complexation. Woldan¹ has described a colorimetric method for the detection of silver in silicates with the help of pyridine. Photometric determination of Mn^{++} has been carried out through chelate formation by Kamp². 2-substituted pyridines have been described as analytical reagents by Sugii and coworkers³. A second important aspect of pyridine derivatives has been their biological activity. Thus Cherkasski and coworkers⁴ have described the fungicidal properties of $CuCl_2$ complexes of pyridine and its derivatives. Hydroxy alkyl-pyridines have been described as growth stimulants by Litvinenko⁵. Aries⁶ has reported Cu^{++} salts of

hydroxy pyridine carboxylic acids as fungicides. A survey of literature has revealed that much study of the metallic complexes of alkyl hydroxy derivatives of pyridine has not been carried so far. In view of the analytical and biological importance of metallic complexes of pyridine derivatives, it was thought worthwhile to investigate the complexation of 2-pyridine ethanol with Zn^{++} and Cd^{++} .

Experimental

2-Pyridine Ethanol (L) was procured from M/S Aldrich Chemical Company, Inc. Milwaukee

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL RESULTS AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA

Complex	Colour & Form	% Metal		% Carbon		% Hydrogen		% Nitrogen		λ_m (Mhos)
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
ZnL_2Cl_2	Cream coloured crystalline	17.12	17.08	43.92	43.89	4.86	4.70	7.01*	7.31]	191.76
ZnL_2Br_2	Yellowish powder	13.61	13.86	35.96	35.62	4.12	3.81	5.78	5.93	236.88
ZnL_2I_2	Dirty yellow powder	11.12	11.56	29.43	29.70	2.76	3.18	4.34	4.95	203.04
$ZnL_2(NO_2)_2$	Yellowish brown Waxy solid	15.56	15.005	38.13	38.55	4.32	4.13	12.72	12.75	203.04
$ZnL_2(SCN)_2$	Blackish brown solid	15.62	15.28	43.35	44.89	4.07	4.20	12.98	13.09	Insoluble
$ZnL_2(OAC)_2$	Orange powder	14.74	15.19	50.32	50.26	4.89	5.58	6.24	6.51	180.48
CdL_2Cl_2	Cream coloured powder	25.72	26.15	39.27	39.09	3.82	4.18	6.45	6.51	191.80
CdL_2Br_2	Creamy coloured shining powder	21.06	21.67	32.09	32.39	3.17	3.47	5.28	5.39	214.32
CdL_2I_2	Dirty white powder	18.03	18.35	27.14	27.42	2.74	2.93	4.62	4.57	225.60
$CdL_2(NO_2)_2$	Yellowish brown waxy solid	23.02	23.28	34.35	34.80	4.00	3.72	11.52	11.60	248.16
$CdL_2(SCN)_2$	Blackish brown solid	23.22	23.67	40.32	40.44	4.12	3.79	11.38	11.79	203.04
$CdL_2(OAC)_2$	Orange solid	23.21	23.57	44.92	45.30	4.86	5.03	5.91	5.87	214.32

TABLE 2—I. R. SPECTRA

L	CdL ₂ Cl ₂ ²	CdL ₂ Br ₂	CdL ₂ I ₂	ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	ZnL ₂ Br ₂	ZnL ₂ I ₂
3226 (m)	3256 (w)	3333 (w)	3333 (m)	3278 (m)	3278 (m)	3333 (m)
2857 (m)	—	2816 (w)	2817 (w)	—	—	—
1600 (s)	1604 (m)	1600 (m)	1600 (m)	1600 (m)	1600 (m)	1600 (m)
1562 (s)	1557 (m)	1552 (m)	1552 (m)	1550 (m)	1550 (m)	1550 (m)
1465 (s)	1483 (m)	1481 (m)	1465 (m)	1480 (m)	1481 (m)	1483 (m)
1388 (m)	—	—	—	—	—	—
1300 (m)	1300 (v.w.)	1300 (w)	1300 (w)	1300 (w)	1300 (w)	1300 (w)
1162 (s)	1162 (m)	1156 (m)	1162 (m)	1156 (m)	1160 (m)	1160 (s)
943 (s)	940 (s)	930 (m)	943 (s)	952 (s)	952 (s)	948 (s)
813 (s)	802 (s)	800 (s)	800 (s) 790 (m)	800 (s) 790 (m)	800 (s) 790 (m)	800 (s) 790 (s)
752 (s)	754 (s)	750 (s)	757 (s)	760 (m) 753 (m)	763 (m) 757 (s)	763 (m) 754 (s)

s—strong, m—medium, w—weak, v.w.—very weak.

Wisconsin-53233 (U.S.A.). All the zinc and cadmium salts used were of A. R. grade. Carbon and hydrogen in the complexes were determined by 'Coleman Analyser'. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. Zinc and cadmium were determined by standard methods. The conductance measurements were carried on WTW conductivity bridge, Type/LBR/2, German make. The results have been provided in Table-1.

The infra-red absorption spectra in the range 4000 cm^{-1} -650 cm^{-1} were recorded on Perkin-Elmer, Model-137, and the results are reported in Table-2. Only chloro-, bromo- and iodo-derivatives were put to i.r. studies.

Preparation of Complexes

Zinc salts containing various anions viz. Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , SCN^- , OAC^- and NO_3^- were refluxed for about 4 hrs. with 'L' in a Metal : ligand ratio of 1 : 2, using 90% ethanolic medium. The resulting solution was then concentrated to reduce its volume and was dried by slow evaporation. The compounds were finally washed with alcohol and dried in vacuo. Cadmium complexes were also prepared by similar methods.

Results and Discussion

Zinc⁷ and Cadmium⁸ complexes of 4-vinyl pyridine have been reported in literature. In these and other derivatives of pyridine, 'N' has been shown to act as the donor atom. In the present investigation the oxygen atom of the ('OH') group provides an additional seat of interaction for coordination to metal ions. The analytical data as provided in Table-1, indicates that the complexes of Zn(II) and Cd(II) with 2-Pyridine-

Ethanol are of the type ML_2X_2 , where $\text{M}=\text{Zn(II)}$ or Cd(II) , $\text{L}=\text{2-Pyridine Ethanol}$ and $\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , SCN^- and OAC^- . λ_m values in 50% alcohol point that all the complexes are 1 : 2 electrolytes confirming the above compositions.

I.R. spectra of the ligand show the characteristic bands of the pyridine ring and the hydroxyl group. The unbonded or 'free' hydroxyl group of alcohols is reported to absorb in the region 3650-3584 cm^{-1} . The appearance of a band at a lower frequency, viz. 3226 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of ligand may be attributed to intermolecular hydrogen bonding. A shift of this band to higher frequencies in the case of complexes is suggestive of weakening of hydrogen bonding and coordination of metal ion through oxygen of the 'OH' group. Ring stretching frequencies in 2-substituted pyridines have been reported to occur in the region 1615-1428 cm^{-1} , and represent interaction of $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching vibrations. The band occurring at 1565 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand is shifted to a lower frequency in all the complexes, while the band at 1465 cm^{-1} is raised to a higher frequency. Also, the band at 1388 cm^{-1} disappears in the spectra of the complexes. These changes in band frequencies suggest that the ligand is not free but is bonded to metal ions through 'Nitrogen'. Coordination through nitrogen is also expected to affect out of plane vibrations of 4-adjacent hydrogen atoms of the ring. In 2-substituted pyridines these vibrations occur in the range 780-740 cm^{-1} . Two intense bands occur at 813 cm^{-1} and 752 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of ligand which may be attributed to the above out of plane vibrations. In general, these bands are found to split and shift to a lower frequency in the spectrum of the complexes. On the basis of above

evidences, following tentative structure for the complexes may be proposed :

Where $M = Zn^{++}$ or Cd^{++} and
 $X = Cl^{-}$, Br^{-} , or I^{-} .

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